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IMPROVING THE APPLICATION OF PREDICTABILITY PRINCIPLE IN THE ACTIVITIES OF SERBIAN LOCAL GOVERNMENTS**

Abstract: *The principle of legitimate expectations is a cornerstone of effective governance both at the national and the local level. It secures legal certainty and safeguards citizens' rightful expectations, significantly enhancing public trust in the operations of local self-governance. This paper analyses the concept of this principle in Serbian legal context, legal sources and norms pertinent to this principle, as well as the mechanisms for its deployment within the local self-government units in Serbia. It scrutinizes various dimensions of administrative predictability, including those founded on legislation, administrative activities, contracts, and notices of the administration. A focal point of consideration in this analysis is the alignment of administrative practices both within and across local self-government units, emphasizing the accessibility and transparency of established legal opinions. The paper emphasizes the significance of standardizing administrative processes, instituting appropriate records, and facilitating information exchange among local governments. The author examines exemplary practices and makes proposals to refine the implementation of the predictability principle in local administration.*

Keywords: *local self-government, principle of legitimate expectations, predictability, legal certainty, harmonizing practices, standardizing procedures.*

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1. Introduction

The principle of legitimate expectations is a cornerstone of modern democratic legal governance. It ensures that citizens can anticipate how public authorities will act, thereby reinforcing legal certainty and promoting public trust. In Serbia, local governments play a crucial role in delivering public services and making decisions that significantly impact everyday life. As such, the principle of legitimate expectations is essential in safeguarding citizens' rights and ensuring that they can rely on consistent and transparent decision-making processes. It is significant both in European administrative law and in national legal systems. In the Republic of Serbia, the General Administrative Procedure Act (GAPA)¹ integrates the principle of predictability into the Serbian administrative law framework. Yet, despite the normative framework, there is a gap in terms of its consistent application at the local government level. As shown later in this paper, researchers have highlighted issues such as inconsistent administrative practices, varying interpretations of legal standards, and a lack of transparency in decision-making processes. These inconsistencies can undermine citizens' trust in local authorities and reduce the predictability of governmental actions, which can be particularly problematic in administrative systems like the Serbian one. Besides, there is limited research on the mechanisms that can improve the implementation of this principle across the country.

The main hypothesis in this paper is that standardizing administrative procedures, improving transparency, and enhancing information-sharing mechanisms among local governments will significantly improve the application of the predictability principle. The aim of this research is to provide a comprehensive framework for improving the implementation of "legitimate expectations" in local governments, and to offer practical recommendations for policymakers and public administrators. Ultimately, this research aims to contribute to enhancing the quality of governance by fostering greater predictability and transparency in local government actions, thereby strengthening the relationship between citizens and public authorities.

2. The Principle of Legitimate Expectations: Definition and theoretical foundations

The principle of legitimate expectations is a fundamental element of good governance, particularly in the context of administrative law. It asserts that individuals have the right to expect that public authorities will act consis-

¹Zakon o opštem upravnom postupku (General Administrative Procedure Act), *Službeni glasnik RS*, 18/2016, 95/2018-autentično tumačenje i 2/2023-odluka US.

tently with previously established legal norms and practices. This principle is derived from the broader concepts of legal certainty and fairness, which are central to democratic governance. According to administrative law scholars, legitimate expectations are a safeguard against arbitrary decision-making, ensuring that citizens can anticipate how government actions will affect their rights and obligations (Craig, 2018: 600-641; Schwarze, 1992: 867-1172).

In legal practice, this principle is established in both national and supranational legal systems. For instance, in European Union law, the Court of Justice of the EU has consistently upheld the principle of legitimate expectations as a means of protecting individuals from abrupt legal changes that could disrupt their rights (Tridimas, 2006: 242-297). In Serbian administrative law, the predictability principle is embedded in the General Administrative Procedure Act, which mandates that administrative bodies, including the local ones, shall adhere to previous decisions in similar cases to ensure consistency (Article 5 of the GAPA).

Historically, in European administrative law, the principle of legitimate expectations was first recognized as a judicial tool to protect citizens from sudden and unjustified changes in policy. The German Administrative Courts were among the first to articulate this principle, particularly in cases related to acquired rights (Milkov, Radošević, 2020: 8-10). Over time, it evolved from a reactive legal protection against retroactive administrative actions to a proactive requirement for transparency and consistency in government operations. In the second part of the 20th century, the European Court of Justice expanded the scope of legitimate expectations to cover not only acquired rights but also the reasonable anticipations of citizens based on existing administrative practices (Tridimas, 2006: 280-285).

The theoretical foundations of legitimate expectations are grounded in the doctrine of the rule of law, particularly the idea that governmental actions should be predictable, transparent, and based on established legal norms. This doctrine emphasizes that public authorities must respect the expectations they have created through their actions, statements, or legal norms. Kantian philosophy provides a deeper theoretical basis, positing that the protection of legitimate expectations is essential for establishing and maintaining trust, social order and fairness between citizens and the state (Picq, 2014, 323). Contemporary administrative law scholars have debated on the scope of this principle, particularly its relationship to other legal doctrines such as legal certainty and fairness. Some argue that legitimate expectations are an extension of legal certainty, while others posit that it is as an independent principle aimed at enhancing the accountability of public authorities (Schwarze, 1992; Tridimas, 2006). The ongoing debate reflects the complex-

ity of the concept and the need for further exploration, particularly in the context of local government administrative practices where inconsistencies can directly impact the citizens and business.

The concept of legitimate expectations was first introduced in Serbian administrative practice in 2010 through the Ombudsman's Code of Good Administration, which was modeled after the EU Code of Good Administrative Behavior (Protector of Citizens, 2011: 26)². Although the document was non-binding, it advised civil servants to consider citizens' legitimate and reasonable expectations, particularly in light of past case law, while also cautioning against creating unrealistic expectations. In the 2011 and 2013 drafts of the General Administrative Procedure Act, the protection of legitimate expectations was proposed as a new principle, requiring administrative bodies to adhere to their previous decisions in similar cases unless a lawful and reasoned justification existed for acting differently. However, in the final version of the General Administrative Procedure Act (GAPA, 2016), this principle was not explicitly designated as "legitimate expectations"; instead, the adopted text focused on the principle of predictability, obliging authorities to consider previous decisions and provide justification for any departures from them (Jerinić, 2021: 117-118). As rightly noted by Jerinić, even though the predictability principle has yet to extend to the protection of legitimate expectations, recognition of the principle by the Serbian Constitutional Court could lead to changes in administrative case law and practice, particularly if similar cases continue to arise before the court. This evolution would show that the principle of legitimate expectations emerges more from case law than from legislation, a development that has not been typical in Serbian jurisprudence (Jerinić, 2021: 125-126).

3. International Legal Rules and Standards on the Principle of Legitimate Expectations

The most important international documents that regulate the principle of legitimate expectations underscore its broad applicability in European public law. The European Convention on Human Rights (ECHR), while not explicitly mentioning legitimate expectations, provides protection which addresses the right to property (Art. 1, Protocol 1 to the ECHR).³ In its case law, the European Court of Human Rights (ECtHR) has interpreted that this provi-

² Protector of Citizens (2011). Regular Annual Report of the Protector of Citizens 2010, Protector of Citizens, Belgrade; <https://www.ombudsman.rs/attachments/article/5560/Annual%20Report%202010.pdf>

³ Article 1, Protocol 1 to the European Convention on Human Rights, ETS 009/1952.

sion encompasses the protection of legitimate expectations, particularly in cases where administrative actions affect an individual's property rights. This interpretation demonstrates how the principle of legitimate expectations is embedded in the broader concept of human rights, further emphasizing its role in protecting citizens from arbitrary state action.

Another key document is the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union (2000), which guarantees the right to good administration (Art. 41 of the CFR).⁴ Although the Charter does not directly enshrine the principle of legitimate expectations, it contains several procedural elements that align with the principle, such as the right to a fair hearing and the obligation for the administration to give reasons for its decisions. The Court of Justice of the EU (CJEU) has consistently reinforced these procedural safeguards in its rulings, ensuring that administrative bodies respect citizens' legitimate expectations in practice. These elements highlight only the procedural nature of legitimate expectations, illustrating how it serves as a procedural guarantee in administrative law. While initially recognized as a procedural guarantee, legitimate expectations can also lead to substantive outcomes, obliging administrative authorities to act in a particular direction based on expectations created by their actions or decisions (Jerinić, 2021: 119).

The European Code of Good Administrative Behaviour (2001), adopted by the European Parliament, explicitly includes legitimate expectations as part of the broader concept of good governance. The Code requires that public officials act consistently and in accordance with established practices, providing clear justifications for any deviations (Art.10 of the Code).⁵ This document formalizes the connection between legitimate expectations and the broader principles of good administration, stressing the importance of consistency and transparency in public administration.

A more recent development is the European Parliament Resolution on Open, Efficient, and Independent EU Administration (2016)⁶, which also promotes the principle of legitimate expectations as part of a broader effort to enhance administrative efficiency and transparency. The Resolution, which includes a draft Regulation for an independent European administration, calls for the codification of the principle in EU law, further emphasizing its significance in ensuring accountable and consistent governance.

⁴ Article 41, the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union, OJ C 326/2012.

⁵ Article 10, the European Code of Good Administrative Behaviour, OJ, L 267/2001.

⁶ European Parliament Resolution of 9 June 2016 for an open, efficient and independent European Union administration (2016/2610(RSP)), OJ C 86/2018.

Another key legal document is the EU Services Directive (2006)⁷, which incorporates legitimate expectations in the context of consumer and business rights. This Directive significantly impacted national legislation, including the Serbian General Administrative Procedure Act (2016). The Directive's focus on protecting the expectations of service recipients reflects the principle's expanding role in both public and private administrative practices across Europe, and further highlights its applicability beyond traditional governance contexts

Finally, the Strategy on Innovation and Good Governance at Local Level (2008)⁸, adopted by the Conference of European Ministers responsible for Local and Regional Government, integrates the principle of legitimate expectations as one of 12 principles of good governance at the local level. This Strategy includes mechanisms for measuring local governments' performance, ensuring that legitimate expectations are established in practice. One such mechanism, the European Label of Governance Excellence (ELoGE), provides a tool for assessing local government efficiency in meeting citizens' expectations. This initiative highlights the importance of the principle of legitimate expectations in fostering trust and accountability in local governance.

4. Legal Framework in Serbia: The Principle of Predictability

The Constitution of the Republic of Serbia (2006)⁹ explicitly guarantees all citizens equal protection of their rights before courts, state bodies and entities exercising public powers, and bodies of the autonomous province or local self-government (Article 36 of the Constitution). This provision requires that all public bodies, including local governments, act uniformly in similar factual and legal circumstances. It mandates that local governments act predictably, avoiding arbitrary decisions that could undermine citizens' rights. However, in practice, Serbia has faced challenges with inconsistent administrative practices across local governments, ultimately leading to varied outcomes in similar cases. The inconsistency has prompted numerous appeals to the Constitutional Court, signaling the need for reforms to enhance uniformity in decision-making (Jerinić, 2021: 125).

The General Administrative Procedure Act (GAPA, 2016) incorporates the principle of predictability into Article 5, titled "The Principle of Legality and

⁷ Directive 2006/123/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council on services in the internal market (The EU Services Directive), *OJ L 376*, 27/12/2006.

⁸ Strategy on Innovation and Good Governance at Local Level, *OJ C 10*, 14/01/2008.

⁹ Ustav Republike Srbije [Constitution of the Republic of Serbia], *Službeni glasnik RS*, br. 98/06.

Predictability.”¹⁰ The GAPA requires that administrative authorities consider prior decisions made in similar cases to ensure consistency in their rulings. This establishes a legal obligation for local governments to harmonize their administrative practices, preventing the unequal treatment of citizens in similar circumstances. The principle of legitimate expectations is further detailed in Article 141 of the GAPA, which outlines the requirement for providing legal reasoning when administrative bodies deviate from established practices, and requires that any decision that departs from common administrative practice must include a clear explanation, detailing the factual and legal basis for the decision (Article 141(§4) of the GAPA).¹¹ This transparency requirement ensures that citizens understand why their case may have been treated differently and allows them to challenge such decisions if they believe their “legitimate expectations” have been violated.

This legal framework becomes even more significant in certain sector-specific areas, where local governments are tasked with delegated responsibilities. For instance, in the context of the Planning and Construction Act,¹² the principle of legitimate expectations is particularly relevant during the issuance of permits, the conduct of inspections, and enforcement actions. Similarly, the Act on Legalization of Buildings¹³ and the Act on Financial Support to Families with Children¹⁴ also highlight the need for consistent administrative practices, especially when determining citizens’ rights to financial support or resolving disputes related to property.

As we can see, the legal framework in Serbia is designed to embed the principle of predictability across multiple administrative sectors. However, the challenge lies in the practical implementation of these legal provisions. The next section will explore the mechanisms available to local governments for ensuring the consistent application of this principle, focusing on best practices and potential reforms aimed at improving predictability in Serbia’s local governance.

¹⁰ Art. 5, Zakon o opštem upravnom postupku [General Administrative Procedure Act], *Sl. glasnik RS*, br. 18/16.

¹¹ Art. 141. Zakon o opštem upravnom postupku [General Administrative Procedure Act], *Sl. glasnik RS*, br. 18/16.

¹² Zakon o planiranju i izgradnji [Planning and Construction Act], *Sl. glasnik RS*, br. 72/09, 132/14, 145/14, 83/18 i 31/19.

¹³ Zakon o ozakonjenju objekata [Legalization of Buildings Act], *Sl. glasnik RS*, br. 96/15.

¹⁴ Zakon o finansijskoj podršci porodici sa decom [Financial Support to Families with Children Act], *Sl. glasnik RS*, br. 113/17 i 50/18.

5. The Principle of Predictability in the context of Local Self-Government in Serbia

The principle of predictability is particularly important in the context of local self-government, where it plays a critical role in ensuring the protection of citizens' rights and consistency of the local administrative actions. In this context, predictability can be understood in two primary ways: first, it ensures that an individual can reasonably expect to exercise rights granted by a final administrative decision; second, it allows individuals to predict how the local government will decide on requests for the recognition of rights. This predictability is not only based on pre-established legal conditions for acquiring rights but also on the prior practices of local government authorities when addressing similar legal and factual matters.

This part of the paper will explore practical mechanisms for realizing these forms of predictability and some additional types, including those based on regulations, contracts, and public statements or actions by local authorities.¹⁵

Predictability in local government often derives from the clarity and transparency of regulations. This form of predictability ensures that local authorities inform individuals about any changes in regulations that may affect their rights, particularly in cases where a final decision that granted rights might be revoked. In such situations, local authorities are expected to explain any deviations from previously established expectations and to provide individuals with the opportunity to respond. The link between the predictability of regulations and transparency is crucial. In theory, predictability is closely linked to the prohibition of retroactivity, meaning that citizens expect that newly introduced regulations will not reduce or revoke their previously acquired rights. However, such expectations may lack legal protection in areas where regulations are subject to frequent changes. Thus, local governments have to carefully assess the time required for citizens to adjust to new normative conditions (Jerinić, Vučetić, Stanković, 2022: 277-278).

An example of this in practice is the phased implementation of the General Administrative Procedure Act (GAPA, 2016) at the national level. Certain provisions of the GAPA came into effect before others, demonstrating a gradual approach to regulatory changes that allowed for better citizen adaptation. Similarly, local governments must ensure that citizens are given sufficient time to comply with new regulations, especially when these affect existing rights.

¹⁵For a more general discussion on these types of predictability principle in administrative law, see Đerđa (2013).

Linking this to the broader legal framework, local government regulations must be in line with both national laws and the Constitution. For instance, Article 194(§3) and Article 195(§2) of the Serbian Constitution mandate that all local regulations must comply with national laws, while Article 195(§3) requires consistency with the statutes of local self-government units. These provisions establish a clear legal hierarchy, ensuring that local regulations do not contradict higher laws, thereby maintaining predictability in administrative decision-making.

Another form of predictability arises from the standardization of administrative procedures. Local government bodies often create internal guidelines or instructions to regulate procedures where there are gaps in both national and local regulations. When these internal procedures are consistently applied and publicly accessible, they can serve as a source of predictability. For instance, the national association of Serbian towns and municipalities (Standing Conference of Towns and Municipalities/SCTM)¹⁶ has developed a register of local administrative procedures. Similar register exists on the national level as well (Vučetić, Dimitrijević, 2021). The goal of such standardization is to ensure that administrative actions are predictable and consistent across different local government units.

Predictability based on administrative practice (case law) refers to the consistency of decisions made by local authorities in similar legal and factual situations. To uphold the principle of equality and prevent discrimination, local governments must ensure that their decisions are aligned across similar cases. Consistency in administrative practices is particularly important in situations where decisions involve discretionary powers. In such cases, while local authorities may have some flexibility in decision-making, they must still provide clear reasoning for any deviation from established practices. The General Administrative Procedure Act¹⁷ requires that any departure from previous decisions be explained in detail, ensuring that citizens understand the reasoning behind such changes. An example of a simple mechanism for achieving consistency in administrative practice is the establishment of forums where officials can discuss new legal issues and collectively decide on how to approach them. This ensures that all officials handling similar cases follow the same approach, thereby enhancing predictability. Examples of good practices can be found in the City of Vranje, where the introduction

¹⁶ Stalna konferencija gradova i opština (n.d.). Modeli administrativnih procedura [Standing Conference of Towns and Municipalities: Models of Administrative Procedures]. <https://www.skgo.org/modeli-administartivnih-procedura>.

¹⁷ Art. 141(4) Zakon o opštem upravnom postupku [General Administrative Procedure Act], *Sl. glasnik RS*, br. 18/16.

of internal forums for discussing legal issues has enhanced the uniformity of decision-making (Jerinić *et al.*, 2022: 286). These forums encourage collaboration among officials, ensuring that similar cases are resolved in a consistent manner. Conversely, bad practices are often observed in municipalities where procedures are either not clearly defined or not consistently followed. In such cases, citizens are unsure about the outcome of their requests, which erodes trust in local authorities. This contrast between good and bad practices underscores the importance of establishing and adhering to clear procedures to maintain predictability in governance (Jerinić *et al.*, 2022: 282-286).

Predictability also extends to contracts, regardless of whether they are business contracts or administrative contracts. Local governments are expected to fulfill their contractual obligations, and any unilateral termination of contracts can violate the principle of predictability. This is particularly relevant in the case of administrative contracts, where there is often an imbalance of power between the contracting parties. Article 22 of the General Administrative Procedure Act defines administrative contracts and outlines the circumstances under which they can be terminated, such as when it is necessary to protect public safety or address economic disruptions. Predictability in contractual relationships is crucial in areas like public procurement, where local governments must ensure that their contractual obligations are clear and consistently upheld (Jerinić *et al.*, 2022: 289)

Finally, predictability can also be derived from public statements, guarantee acts, and administrative actions. The General Administrative Procedure Act regulates guarantee acts (Articles 18-21 of the GAPA), which are defined as written acts obliging public authorities to issue administrative acts of a certain content upon an appropriate party's request (Art. 18 of the GAPA). These guarantees provide citizens with legal certainty, as they can rely on the local government to act predictably in accordance with the guarantee. In situations where local governments publicly announce certain actions or policies, citizens base their expectations on these statements. For instance, if a local government announces a public service initiative, citizens reasonably expect that the initiative will be carried out as planned. Failure to meet these expectations can result in a loss of trust in local authorities.

To improve the implementation of the principle of predictability within the local government system, the national association of Serbian towns and municipalities (the Standing Conference of Towns and Municipalities/ SCTM) has developed several mechanisms for assessing the efficiency of local gov-

ernance. One of the major tools is the Index of Good Governance at the Local Level.¹⁸

The Index of Good Governance at the Local Level monitors seven indicators to analyze the degree of predictability in the work and actions of each local self-government unit: standardization of administrative practice within a local self-government unit, standardization of administrative practice between different local self-government units, control of the process of standardizing administrative practices, availability of standardized administrative practices, delivery of responses from first-instance bodies to appeals, informing parties about regulatory changes during proceedings, and tracking the progress of cases. The seven indicators were measured on three different occasions (in 2018, 2021 and 2023) in 60 local governments (14 cities and 46 municipalities); in this period, the overall score for all 60 local governments improved from 34.61% to 45.56%, out of the maximum 100%. The 2023 study indicates that only 3.3% of local governments lack any mechanisms for standardizing administrative practices, which is a significant improvement when compared to 15% in 2021 and 45% in 2018. However, there is still room for further improvement of standardization, especially between different local governments and in monitoring this process. Another significant achievement was the high compliance with the indicator concerning the submission of responses by first-instance bodies to appeals in 100% of analyzed local governments, which was likely influenced by existing penal provisions. Other types of predictability have also been improved, such as notifying parties of changes in regulations. Tracking the progress of cases is another indicator that may show further advancement in the future, particularly due to the introduction of information technology in the execution of administrative procedures (SCTM, 2024: 18).

6. Conclusion

Predictability is an important principle of good local governance which is characteristic of modern local self-governments that strive to go beyond mere compliance with the principle of legality. Predictability increases citizens' satisfaction with life in their local community; on the one hand, it

¹⁸Stalna konferencija gradova i opština (2024). *Analiza učinka i kapaciteta jedinica lokalnih samouprava u primeni principa dobrog upravljanja na lokalnom nivou korišćenjem „Indeksa dobre uprave“: Izvod iz analize* [Analysis of the Performance and Capacity of Local Self-Government Units in Implementing Good Governance Principles at the Local Level Using the “Good Governance Index”: Excerpt from Analysis; SCTM], Partner Solutions, januar 2024; https://www.skgo.org/storage/app/uploads/public/170/834/020/1708340204_Analiza%20ucinka%20dobro%20upravljanje%202023Izvod.pdf

ensures respect for acquired rights and legal certainty; on the other hand, it enables citizens and businesses to plan ahead and adjust their behavior to the announced changes in the local self-government system in the places where they live and work. Therefore, it is very important to understand the basic types of predictability and their content. We have categorized predictability into two basic types: 1) legal predictability of regulations, decisions, contracts, guarantee acts, practices), and 2) material predictability of actions, statements, notifications).

Local governments in Serbia face numerous challenges when implementing the principle of predictability (legitimate expectations). One of the main challenges in implementing this principle lies in the legal gaps and ambiguities within the regulatory framework. Many local governments operate under the regulations that fail to provide clear guidance for handling certain administrative matters. Another significant challenge is the lack of capacity and resources in local self-governments. Many municipalities are underfunded and understaffed, which makes it difficult to maintain the administrative infrastructure necessary for consistent decision-making. Limited access to legal expertise and technological resources further exacerbates this problem, as officials may not have the tools they need to apply the law uniformly. For example, in smaller municipalities, the lack of digital systems for tracking administrative processes often leads to delays and inconsistent outcomes, thus undermining the predictability of governance. The level of expertise and training of local government officials also poses a challenge. In many cases, officials lack the specialized knowledge required to handle complex administrative matters in a predictable manner. This variability in expertise is also problematic in smaller municipalities, where training opportunities may be limited.

To resolve these challenges, the National Association of Serbian Towns and Municipalities has developed several key mechanisms to enhance predictability and standardization in the work of local governments. One of the primary tools is the Index of Good Governance at the Local Level, which monitors seven essential predictability indicators in key Serbian local governments.

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**УНАПРЕЂЕЊЕ ПРИМЕНЕ ПРИНЦИПА ПРЕДВИДИВОСТИ У РАДУ
ЈЕДИНИЦА ЛОКАЛНЕ САМОУПРАВЕ**

Резиме

Принцип предвидивости представља један од кључних компоненти ефикасног управљања на локалном нивоу. Он омогућава поштовање правне сигурности и заштиту легитимних очекивања грађана, чиме се доприноси повећању поверења јавности у рад локалне самоуправе. У овом раду аутор дефинише појам принципа предвидивости у контексту управног поступања, врши анализу правних извора и стандарда који се односе на принцип предвидивости, као и механизма за његову примену у оквиру јединица локалне самоуправе у Србији. Разматрају се различити аспекти предвидивости, укључујући оне засноване на законодавству, управној пракси, уговорима и обавештењима управе. Посебна пажња посвећена је механизмима за хармонизацију управне праксе како унутар тако и међу јединицама локалне самоуправе, као и доступности и транспарентности усвојених правних ставова. Рад истиче значај стандардизације административних процедура, успостављања одговарајућих евиденција и размене информација међу локалним самоуправама. Такође, анализирају се примери добре праксе и износе препоруке за унапређење примене принципа предвидивости с циљем јачања правне сигурности и поверења грађана у делатност локалних власти.

Кључне речи: локална самоуправа, принцип предвидивости, добро управљање, правна сигурност, легитимна очекивања, уједначавање праксе, стандардизација поступака.

